

¹³⁸ Ivi, p. 342.

¹³⁹ Secondo P. DAN, *Histoire de Barbarie et de ses corsaire, des Royaumes et des villes de Alger, Tunis, de Salé et de Tripoly*, 1646 (II ed.), pp. 170-171.

¹⁴⁰ Questa la spiegazione di Ibn Abi Dinar, citata da PIGNON, *Osta Moratto Turcho Genovese* cit., p. 352.

CONTESTED SUBJECTHOOD

RUNAWAY SLAVES IN EARLY MODERN VENICE*

This article considers four cases of runaway domestic slaves in Venice, spanning the period 1573 to 1649, to explore the varying assumptions about subjecthood, religious conversion, and transgression that went into the making and unmaking of bondage. Although rare, the archival traces left by early modern runaway slaves suggest that in their quest for freedom, domestic slaves had not only to sever one set of ties, but to cultivate another. The multiple narrations of slaves' trajectories before and after enslavement that form part of various official genres of documentation further allow us to explore the differing conceptions of subjection that runaway slaves and their interlocutors articulated. Moving beyond juridical definitions of freedom and slavery, this study emphasizes the myriad social mechanisms that shaped a sense of membership and marginality among subaltern subjects. In particular, it underscores the complex trans-imperial nexus that both sustained early modern Mediterranean slavery and at times disrupted it.

In 1670, a 32-year old man named Pierantonio approached the Venetian Patriarch, seeking permission to get married. Given his foreign provenance, Pierantonio was asked to provide witnesses to attest to his unmarried status, before such permission could be granted¹. He was able to summon eight witnesses, all men, who had known him at different moments in his long Italian sojourn, from a 10-year old slave-boy in southern Italy to a veteran Venetian mariner and soldier. As the cases below suggest, this density of «relational resources», to borrow Simona Cerutti's famous phrase, typified other slaves and former slaves in Venice, and belies their presumed axiomatic isolation². Pierantonio was born as Omar, son of Bechir Dumancic in Zemonico (Zemunik Donji), a small Ottoman town bordering the Venetian Dalmatian stronghold of Zara (Zadar, now in Croatia). As a young boy, Omar and his teenaged sister Maire were enslaved, along with at least two dozen other women and children of the same town. Many of them,

including Maire, found their way to Venice, where, from 1647 to 1653 they were baptized in the House of Catechumens, an institution established in 1557 to prepare Muslims and Jews for baptism³. Young Omar, on the other hand, was gifted or sold to Pierantonio Melazzi, the Canon of Bisceglie, a town on the southern Italian Adriatic coast, just north of Bari in the Spanish-controlled Kingdom of Naples. In 1648, at the age of ten, Omar was baptized in Bisceglie's cathedral with his master's nephew and niece serving as his godparents, and assumed Melazzi's Christian name. Upon baptism, he moved to the house of Melazzi's brother, Francesco, the Baron of Bisceglie, where he stayed for several more years. In the meantime, his sister became a domestic slave in the household of Andrea Nalosich of Zara, a well-to-do ship's captain based in Venice⁴. In 1649, at sixteen, Maire was baptized in the House of Catechumens and given the name Antonia, after having been catechized in Nalosich's home. She became his wife soon after⁵. This union offered Maire's brother Pierantonio new opportunities, and a few years later, as a young man in his twenties, he left Bisceglie for Venice to become a mariner on board the ship of his brother-in-law, whom he joined on three trips to Izmir. Pierantonio later travelled to Alexandria on another ship, similarly owned by a Dalmatian captain, and eventually served in two Venetian naval campaigns under Simon Nalosich, Andrea's grandson. Now, upon returning to Venice, he wished to get married.

This anticipated marriage occasioned a set of testimonies on his behalf, including those of his seventy-year old brother-in-law, Andrea, and Nalosich's twenty-something grandson, Simon. These testimonies allow us to gain a glimpse into the complex trajectories and patronage networks that shaped Omar/Pierantonio's life, like those of many other slaves and former slaves in early modern Venice⁶. The very production of such records – and the uses to which they were put in determining foreigners' eligibility to marry in the city – reinforce the paramount importance of spiritual kinship and affinal ties to former slaves as paradigmatic foreigners in early modern Catholic societies. As I have argued elsewhere, in a commercially-oriented imperial metropole like Venice, which witnessed continuous waves of migration from the Ottoman borderlands as well as from trans-Alpine Europe, the patronage networks spawned via the baptismal sponsorship of converts helped facilitate spatial and social mobility within and across imperial borders⁷. This was doubly true for slaves, whose access to other types of relational resources, and especially to their natal kin, was deemed particularly limited⁸.

Indeed, Omar/Pierantonio's case suggests ways in which enslavement as a child could actually facilitate effective forms of social, as well

as spatial mobility, while curtailing others. His long years of service as a baptized slave were eventually rewarded by formal manumission, the acquisition of a trade, and insertion into a network of patronage that secured his ability to forge new kinship ties in Venice. It is quite possible that his links to Nalosich were established already at the moment of his capture. As mentioned, Nalosich hailed from Zara, a very short distance from Omar's hometown of Zemonico. This spatial proximity, and the fact that Nalosich was involved in the rapid baptism of several other slaves from the same town besides his future bride, may suggest his role as an intermediary who facilitated the slaves' physical and social crossing from Ottoman to Venetian territory⁹. Such mediated crossing helped to incorporate slaves into a Christian moral community, and defined to a large extent the limits of their access to Venetian social spaces and civic institutions. Removed from their natal kin and prevented – at least while in bondage – from forging new licit kinship ties, the patronage of a master or a former master often proved paramount in a young slave's life.

In Omar/Pierantonio's case, the transition from freedom to slavery and back to freedom may have cemented his bond to one specific patron, reminding us of the frequently blurred line between commerce, kinship, and patronage in the early modern Mediterranean. But for many other domestic slaves in Venice, freedom necessitated not only the severance of one set of ties, but the cultivation of a new one. Like Omar's, the stories of these slaves allow us to explore the varying assumptions about subjecthood, community, and affect that went into the making and unmaking of bondage in early modern societies, moving us beyond juridical definitions of freedom and slavery to the myriad social mechanisms that cultivated a sense of belonging among subaltern subjects. The cases presented below also gesture towards the complex trans-imperial nexus that undergirded contemporary understandings of membership and marginality.

To understand this nexus, it is necessary first to consider Venetian domestic slavery more generally, and the role of slaves in Venetian articulations of subjecthood in the context of the early modern Mediterranean. The general pattern sketched here is based largely on the extant archival records of institutions, such as the *Pia casa dei catechumeni* (House of Catechumens), the Venetian Holy Office, the *Cinque savii alla mercanzia* (Board of Trade), and government reports and decrees. Such archives were produced to support specific forms of governmentality and therefore mainly reflect the logic, classificatory schemas, and interests of their producers. To give a few examples, Venetian magistracies typically used the term «turco» indiscriminately to refer to Ot-

toman Muslim subjects, regardless of ethnicity or place of provenance. Similarly, they tended to assume that slaves had been cut off from extra-Venetian social worlds, and rarely paid any attention to slaves' social standing prior to their capture, or to their possible ongoing ties to such worlds (facilitated, *inter alia*, by the written and oral communication practices of highly-mobile Ottoman and Safavid merchants). As a result, our knowledge of slaves' experiences in early modern Venice is not simply anecdotal and piecemeal, but heavily curtailed by the very categories of knowledge that underlay the production of the documentation in the first place. This goes above and beyond the multiple levels of scribal mediation and generic formulas that have made it virtually impossible to tease out an unmediated slave perspective – it calls into question the very enterprise of distilling slave voices from documents and archival genres that were «composite» and patrician to the core. That said, it is still instructive to follow the archival traces left by runaway slaves. Through them, we are able to gain insights into competing configurations of confessional, juridical, and social belonging, and the specific ways in which the routes to escape were themselves shaped by individuals' social – as much as legal and confessional – identities¹⁰.

Medieval legislation prohibited the sale of slaves in Venetian markets and urged the liberation of slaves within four years of their capture. Yet slavery was prevalent throughout premodern Venetian territory¹¹. Although scholars of Venice have suggested that slavery was on the decline by the sixteenth century, there is much evidence to indicate a significant slave presence in early modern Venetian society. In addition to a sizable population of galley slaves, contemporary patrician households also relied on domestic slaves, including enslaved children and youth¹². These slaves hailed from Sub-Saharan and North Africa, the Black Sea region, and various territories along the Venetian-Ottoman border in the Adriatic and Aegean. The fashion for black slaves, especially children, was at its height in the late fifteenth century, but there is also consistent evidence of «moors» as slaves in Venetian households throughout the seventeenth century¹³.

If in theory Christians could not be enslaved by other Christians, the archives reveal time and again that some Venetians were far from scrupulous in purchasing slaves who could reasonably claim to be of Christian provenance¹⁴. Similarly, the theological injunction to manumit slaves upon baptism was only sporadically followed in practice. In the wake of the Catholic Reformation, the concerted effort to baptize domestic slaves, alongside other «infidels», did not diminish the number of slaves in Venice: Governors of the House of Catechumens did

occasionally attempt to release slaves from galley service or from prison in preparation for their baptism. But there does not seem to have been any general policy of manumitting the newly baptized, whether from galley or domestic service¹⁵. The baptismal records of many slaves in fact mention explicitly their return to their old masters and mistresses upon baptism. In this as in other respects, early modern Venice displayed clear continuities with medieval Mediterranean slavery.

But, more than in medieval times, early modern Venetian domestic slavery also had a particular inter-imperial dimension, as the vast majority of domestic slaves were subjects of the Ottoman sultan. While the specific provenance of slaves (e.g. North Africa, the Black Sea region, the Dalmatian hinterlands and the Aegean islands) may not have fundamentally changed by the sixteenth century, the fact that these regions were now all part of an expanding Ottoman state, where slavery was widespread (and perceived by Venetians as a key to Ottoman political and military success), did shift the meaning of slavery in Venice¹⁶. Beyond the particularities of specific master-slave relations, the very presence of slaves of Ottoman provenance in Venetian homes was understood to reciprocate the enslavement of Venetian subjects in the Ottoman Empire, especially by corsairs based in Ottoman North Africa¹⁷. Corsairing was, of course, not a uniquely Ottoman practice. Several Catholic Orders and groups, with the tacit cooperation of the Habsburgs, Venetians, and French, engaged in it as well, using similar imperial (and religious) justifications. Indeed, to some extent the intra-Mediterranean slave trade thrived well into the early modern period precisely because of this *quid pro quo* logic¹⁸. Significantly, both Ottomans and Venetians counted their imperial rivalry partially in terms of slaves taken and returned. Aiding runaways, then, could be seen by members of both societies as an expression of religious piety, but also as a concrete contribution to a complex geopolitical struggle, an act that might gain one merit with the sovereign. Expectations about the status of slaves, their prospects, their *habitus*, and their capacity to be re-integrated as freed persons into their societies of provenance were to some extent shared across Venetian and Ottoman spaces.

To explore these issues, below I first sketch out – in chronological order – four Venetian cases involving runaway slaves of Ottoman provenance, spanning the period 1570 to 1650. I then suggest that this chronology might reveal a subtle transformation in slaves' access to social networks that could facilitate their escape in the wake of the establishment of an Ottoman Exchange House, the *Fondaco dei Turchi*, in 1621. This institution, serving as a highly visible emblem of the Ottoman Muslim presence in the city, was also a heavily guarded, enclosed space

that helped strengthen the conceptual link between Ottoman juridical and religious alterity and runaway slaves' social transgression.

Our first, and by far most well-documented case, is that of a teenaged slave named Zorzi, who in the summer of 1573 ran away from the house of his patrician master and allegedly apostatized. When word of the matter reached the Venetian Holy Office in early August, it promptly launched an investigation¹⁹. According to the initial deposition, Zorzi, formerly a Muslim, had been baptized and had received communion and other holy sacraments. But now, having gone into hiding in the attic of a house «where several Turks live», he allegedly returned to Islam («tornato a far Turco») «having shaved his head and dressed as a Turk in order to go secretly to Turkey». Five days after the escape, Zorzi's master, Marcantonio Falier, visited his place of hiding²⁰. He was met by a defiant landlord, a Greek commercial broker named Francesco di Demetri Lettino, but better known by his nickname, Frangia, and his wife, Giulia. The couple claimed complete ignorance of Zorzi's whereabouts, but Falier persisted in demanding that his slave be returned. That evening Frangia sent Zorzi to spend the night at a friend's house nearby, and the following morning the slave was unceremoniously returned to his master²¹.

Despite this «happy ending» from Falier's point of view, and the apparent restoration of Venetian social order, the Holy Office did not drop the case. Rather, it arrested Frangia, and opened a lengthy investigation, in the course of which the inquisitors interrogated not only Zorzi, but also Frangia, Giulia, their 18-year old son, as well as a neighbor and a family friend. Their depositions reveal the deep tensions between how inquisitors and witnesses drew moral, religious, and social boundaries between Venetians and Turks, Christians and Muslims, masters and slaves. They also underscore the important role of diffuse networks of what I call *trans-imperial subjects*, including merchants, slaves, interpreters, and brokers, in the process of mediating these categories, defining and re-defining their contours²². Specifically, the various testimonies bespeak a complex set of interests, hierarchies of authority, and modes of interaction between locals, localized foreigners (like Frangia himself), and Ottoman sojourners. Such interactions clearly violated patrician ideologies of a perfected social order premised on Christian morality and civic unity in the face of religious and juridical Others.

Indeed, the unfolding narratives produced by the various witnesses summoned to court in 1573 reveal how specific trans-imperial subjects – including Frangia, Giulia, Zorzi, Ottoman merchants and their slaves

– were embedded in extensive social networks that stretched well beyond Venice. As importantly, these narratives suggest the transgressive nature of Frangia's domestic arrangements, at least from the point of view of his patrician interrogators²³. Such arrangements belie a simple parsing of their milieu into «Venetian» and «Turkish», and underscore the role of localized *émigrés*, such as Frangia and Giulia, in facilitating a range of interactions across linguistic, confessional, and juridical boundaries. Key testimony to the prevalence of transgressive domestic arrangements was provided by none other than the escaped slave himself. Zorzi claimed that he had planned to go back to the Ottoman Empire in the hope of finding his Christian Bulgarian parents, whom he had not seen since his capture as a young boy. He had been encouraged to run away from his Venetian master, he said, by several friends of similar circumstances. All of them had purportedly managed to escape Venice on board a ship heading for Izmir just a few days earlier, assisted along the way not only by Ottoman merchants and their slaves, but also by Frangia's family²⁴.

From the beginning of the proceedings, then, Zorzi presented himself as reluctant to abide by the rules governing Venetian domestic slavery. Rather than endorse his new identity as a baptized slave, he asserted his wish to return to his *ur* identity – not that of a Muslim enemy subject, but that of a kidnapped Christian boy. To that end, he related how he had recruited an extended network of accomplices, crossing spatial, social, and religious boundaries. His professed desire to reunite with his parents was, moreover, a powerful indictment of his current servile state, challenging the legality of his very enslavement²⁵. In order to befriend Frangia's tenants, the Ottoman merchants, and secure their assistance in his escape, Zorzi implied he was even willing to «reactivate» his Muslim past and resume Muslim bodily practices such as head-shaving and the donning of a white turban²⁶. It is impossible of course to determine what exactly transpired between Zorzi and his Ottoman-Muslim hosts in Frangia's house, but Zorzi was apparently convincing enough in invoking a Muslim background for the merchants to collaborate in his (ultimately abortive) attempt to return to the Ottoman Empire. Zorzi's testimony and the actions it described speak to his command of several sets of practices associated with different ethno-religious categories of belonging in the Venetian-Ottoman borderlands, and their attendant narrative frames. Such mastery allowed this young person some flexibility in negotiating the juridical and political constraints on his status as a domestic slave.

If Zorzi's testimony poked holes in patrician representations of a perfected Venetian social and religious order, other witnesses similarly

undermined notions of a stable patriarchal domestic order. Throughout the trial, Frangia, the commercial broker, sought to present himself as the master of an orderly household, and to claim authority over his wife, children, and tenants. But two revelations seriously compromised his claims to authority: that the keys to the house were actually kept by his Ottoman tenants, and that as a broker-landlord he was utterly dependent on the translation skills of these tenants' slaves, for he himself did not speak a word of Turkish²⁷. Not only did the slaves possess vital communicative skills, but their friendship with a diverse group of young slaves, servants, and apprentices across the city gave them broad access to several social *milieus*, belying their presumed isolation. Furthermore, these slaves apparently exerted enough authority to conduct Zorzi's ceremonial head shaving, an act that transgressed not only religious, but social hierarchies as well. It mirrored and reversed Zorzi's baptism by his patrician master only eighteen months earlier, an important ritual enactment of ownership and supposed spiritual transformation²⁸.

As if these revelations were not enough, the inquisitors persisted to express concern not only over Zorzi's planned escape and ostensible apostasy, but over the moral well-being of Frangia's family itself, locating the danger precisely in the crossing of social and spatial boundaries between his kin and tenants. Specifically, the inquisitors questioned at length Frangia's wife. They wished to know about eating and sleeping arrangements in her house, which they construed as a site of scandalous mixing²⁹. Soon thereafter, Frangia himself shrewdly stressed the need to prevent such mixing, thus striking a sympathetic chord with the authorities. A year after his trial, Frangia forcefully alluded to «scandals» caused by the lodging of Muslim merchants in Christian households when he petitioned the government to grant him an exclusive privilege to operate a *fondaco* (exchange-house, from the Arabic *funduq*) for «Turks», a «special hotel, like the ones of many other Nations, and people in this city, and also like the ones the Turks in their countries of the Levant have provided for the Christian Nation». His request was granted in 1575, and a hostel, and later a more formal *Fondaco dei Turchi*, were operated by Frangia's descendants for at least a century thereafter³⁰. As I have argued elsewhere, these institutions and their attendant logic of segregation and containment helped consolidate the boundary between the social categories of «Ottoman» and «Venetian»³¹. At the same time, they also created new possibilities for runaway slaves and others to transgress this very boundary. In closing, we should also note Frangia's and Zorzi's striking ability, as paradigmatic trans-imperial subjects, to use their presumed knowledge of foreign practices to authorize their actions in Venice. This pattern of

explicit or implicit mediation typified other runaway slaves and their accomplices as well³².

Zorzi was hardly the last slave appearing in front of the Venetian Holy Office to tell a story of abduction and religious conversion at a tender age. In 1591, a slave named Bastian of Kotor (Montenegro) arrived in Venice along with his Ottoman master. He soon escaped the latter and arrived at the House of Catechumens, where he claimed to have been kidnapped from his Christian parents as a 10-year old boy. Now, having been brought to the House by «two Christians», he was promptly reconciled with the Church, confessed and communicated, and sent to Kotor as a soldier under Captain Domenico da Revera, perhaps in anticipation of reuniting with his family of origin³³. The House of Catechumens not infrequently placed young male neophytes in military service, particularly on the Ottoman border. Such placements both heightened the notion of «holy war» in the decades after Lepanto, and provided ready forms of integration for new converts in an imperial web of patronage that extended from Venice literally to the edges of empire³⁴. In the case of someone like Bastian, the bittersweet ironies of returning to his natal territory as a free person at arms against his captors were probably not lost on his patrons either.

The trope of the Ottoman slave as a kidnapped Christian child certainly circulated in both directions (and reverberated in other parts of the Mediterranean as well). In 1585 the Holy Office heard testimonies on the alleged Venetian provenance of Rustone, a young Ottoman slave, perhaps 25 years old at the time, who had been visiting Venice regularly with his master for a few years³⁵. The young man returned to Venice repeatedly, but, while acknowledging his Venetian origin, showed no interest in either resettling in the city permanently, reconciling with the Church, or obtaining manumission. This «reluctance» may have resulted from the different understandings and social implications of domestic slavery in Venetian and in Ottoman contexts. The Ottoman military and bureaucratic elites of this period emerged predominantly from among the sultan's personal slaves (*kuls*), thus undermining any clear correlation between juridical servile status and social marginality. Moreover, unlike their Venetian counterparts, Ottoman domestic slaves often operated as public, trusted representatives of their masters, and commonly engaged in a variety of occupations outside the household (as, indeed, did Rustone in his capacity as a traveling trader), where their daily activities were not monitored by their master³⁶. This public presence of domestic slaves throughout the Ottoman Empire, and the range of opportunities that their mobility afforded to attain both skill, power, and wealth, clearly fostered a very different self-understanding among

slaves. It seems that Rustone considered the opportunities opened up by his transformation from a free Venetian subject to an Ottoman slave sufficient to forgo manumission and reconciliation with the Church.

Another important difference between the status of Venetian and Ottoman domestic slaves is not to be missed. In Bastian's case (and in Rustone's, had he chosen to leave his master) the claim to have been kidnapped from Christian parents at a young age was compelling ground for a quick reconciliation with the Church and release from bondage in Venice. Yet this was hardly the case for Zorzi, whose master was not a sojourning Ottoman merchant, but a member of the Venetian patriciate. This underscores the dependence of the category «slave» on a much broader, trans-imperial field of power, where a slave's status and horizon of geographical, social, and juridical mobility clearly depended on that of his or her master.

Our third runaway slave fled his master several decades after Zorzi's botched escape and Bastian's successful one. Testimonies in Zorzi's case revealed how embedded Ottoman subjects in fact could be in Venetian society, and the ways in which slaves of Ottoman provenance occasionally participated in a range of Venetian networks. The following case captures a different moment, perhaps signaling – at least anecdotally – an important shift in the experience of Muslim slaves in the aftermath of the establishment of a permanent Exchange-House for Ottoman (and eventually all Muslim) merchants in Venice. By 1636, Frangia's descendants had been operating an establishment for decades, first as a makeshift hostel, for some Ottoman merchants, and from 1621 on as the *Fondaco dei Turchi*, where all Muslim merchants regardless of juridical affiliation were eventually required to reside under the law. When the authorities learned of the escape of another slave from a high-profile master, the *Avogador di Comun* Marino Bragadin, the stakes were quite higher than in 1573. Given restrictions on entrance into the *Fondaco*, and the well-organized opposition expected once inside, a private mission by the master to retrieve his slave – as in Zorzi's case – was now out of the question. Instead, the Venetian government tried to send into the compound interpreters, commercial brokers, and, finally, an armed force. Unlike Zorzi's rapid retrieval from Frangia's house, efforts to convince the merchants inside the *Fondaco* to turn Bragadin's slave over to the authorities for interrogation bore fruit only after several days of intense negotiations, cajoling, and threats³⁷. The *Fondaco* may have offered a clear focal point to domestic slaves of Ottoman-Muslim background who were dispersed around the city, a spatial and spiritual anchor in a post-Tridentine environment that was otherwise hardly sympathetic to their plight. But it also made it easier to capture run-

away slaves, whose tracks often led to the highly-visible and closely monitored space of the *Fondaco*. Ultimately, the accumulation of cases of runaway slaves seeking temporary refuge in the *Fondaco* may have strengthened its perception in the eyes of Venetian authorities as the site not only of religious difference, but of social transgression as well, further contributing to the conflation of religious and juridical alterity in the figure of the «Turk».

A few years after Bragadin's slave sought refuge in the *Fondaco*, a young boy named «Assolomamuto» of Rhodes was captured by the Knights of Malta and sold to a member of the order, whom he served as a domestic slave first on Malta, then in Siena, for a total of nine years³⁸. In 1649, at age 25, after he managed to run away and arrive in Venice, Assolomamuto was taken under the wing of an Ottoman Muslim merchant, one Mustafa Çelebi, who tried to place him with a new, Muslim master who might sneak him out of the city. But the second attempt resulted in the young slave's arrest. The authorities claimed he in fact had been baptized. That he had been sighted walking around the city dressed as a Christian – at least according to Armenian merchants' reports – certainly did not help his case. In his defense, the slave claimed that he had always been a Muslim, that he wished to return to the Ottoman Empire, that while in Siena he had donned Muslim garb, and that he only dressed as a Christian in Venice so as not to be recognized as a runaway slave. He was still charged with apostasy³⁹. This case underscores once again the trans-imperial dimensions of early modern Venetian slavery. Not only was Assolomamuto's trajectory on the Italian peninsula shaped by the complex commercial-cum-confessional web of interests that typified seventeenth-century Mediterranean corsairing, but his planned-for escape crucially relied on the patronage of several Ottoman merchants. Finally, his conviction with apostasy was based on the testimonies of Armenian merchants, whose own juridical status is unknown. Whether Ottoman, Safavid, or indeed Venetian subjects, Armenian merchants certainly played an important role as witnesses in such cases, often using their trans-imperial contacts, distant provenance, and command of Turkish and Persian to warrant general pronouncements about «Levantine» habits, customs, and religions⁴⁰.

As the four cases outlined above suggest, runaway slaves in early modern Venice did not operate in a space composed of discrete individuals pertaining to predetermined social categories. Rather, slaves, masters, and members of a host of religious and civic institutions actively participated in shaping what came to be seen as acceptable slave subjectivities, and the conditions for the legitimate and successful contestation of bondage. The categories of «slavery» and «freedom» grad-

ually crystallized through a myriad of practices, constrained and enabled by the matrix of power of the Venetian-Ottoman borderlands. In other words: slavery was defined not only by jurists and legislators, and not simply in contrast to freedom as the paradigmatic property of the Venetian citizen, but through the multiple interactions between Venetian and Ottoman political and juridical discourses and the practices of slaves, slave-owners, and various other intermediaries in this trans-imperial field of power⁴¹.

In all four cases discussed here, domestic spaces, whether private, like the home of the broker Frangia and his wife Giulia, or institutionalized, like the House of Catechumens or the *Fondaco dei Turchi*, played a crucial role in defining the extent of a slave's potential patronage network, and the possibility of transformation into a free person. Such spaces themselves belied neat categorization as either Venetian or Ottoman. When Frangia and Giulia welcomed Muslim Ottoman tenants into their home and entrusted them with the house keys, when they allowed their young child to roam about on the staircase leading to the tenants' quarter, when they tacitly accepted runaway slaves hiding in their attic, and when they lied to their Venetian patrician interlocutors both at home and at court, they re-drew important social boundaries in ways that clearly transgressed patrician notions of what was moral, honorable, and legal. Later, when Frangia petitioned the government to allow him to operate a *fondaco* for Muslim merchants, he sought to capitalize on precisely those increasingly-threatened boundaries of the Venetian moral community. His petition (and, eventually, his alleged maltreatment of tenants as the *Fondaco's* manager) set in motion a host of other processes and intermediaries, which ultimately led to an ever more consolidated spatial and conceptual segregation between Venetian and Ottoman subjects, between Christians and Muslims, and between different categories of Ottoman subjects operating in Venice. These reconstituted boundaries were in part the result of such actions, rather than their precondition.

The cases outlined here also attest to the resurgent role of religion in the seventeenth-century Mediterranean, as a yardstick by which some enslaved subjects were deemed to be «miscategorized» and hence deserving emancipation. What is novel about this religious resurgence is not so much the Venetian conflation of Muslim identity and servile juridical status, but rather the institutionalization of rapid procedures for the adjudication of claims by runaway slaves to have been born to Christian parents, and baptized at birth. In this sense, the language of religious conversion provided the most readily available idiom for facilitating social and physical mobility, enabling (or at least setting the

groundwork for) transition from bondage to freedom and from one imperial domain to another.

These cases therefore illustrate the specific role of runaway slaves and their multiple interlocutors in articulating differing conceptions of juridical subjection, religious conversion, and social transgression, within and across early modern Mediterranean empires. Finally, these cases, anecdotal and brief as they may be, suggest that a shift in the power balance between Venetian officialdom and Ottoman sojourners may have taken place with the establishment of the *Fondaco dei Turchi*, and the localization of a significant group of semi-permanent Ottoman and Safavid merchants in Venice. By the 1630s, runaway slaves who sought to flee their Venetian masters could hope – by simply reaching the *Fondaco* – to gain the patronage of an ever more self-conscious Ottoman and Safavid community. Such patronage, however, hardly sufficed to circumvent Venetian categories and practices of subject formation altogether. The itinerary that led runaway slaves to the *Fondaco* was also the one the authorities could most easily anticipate and intercept. The few cases that are recorded in the archives represent failed escapes, but it is quite possible that – as the slave Zorzi intimated to the inquisitors in 1573 – many others in similar conditions had, in fact, fled the city.

E. NATALIE ROTHMAN

Note al testo

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¹ For a discussion of the genre of *Examinum Matrimoniorum* as a source for converted slaves' itineraries in early modern Venice, see E.N. ROTHMAN, *Brokering empire: trans-imperial subjects between Venice and Istanbul*, Ithaca 2011, pp. 108-13.

² S. CERUTTI, *Giustizia e località a Torino in età moderna. Una ricerca in corso*, in «Quaderni storici», 89 (1995), pp. 445-86. For a sustained discussion of the tension between alienation and integration in early modern Mediterranean slavery, see G. FIUME, *Schiavitù mediterranee: corsari, rinnegati e santi di età moderna*, Milano 2009, pp. 58-9 and passim.

³ See Archivio Storico del Patriarcato di Venezia (henceforth: ASPV), *Curia Patriarcale di Venezia. Sezione Antica, Catechumini, Registri battesimi* (henceforth: CRb), reg. 2, f. 20r (April 23, 1647), f. 20v (April 25, 1647, May 8, 1647), f. 21v (Oct. 24, 1647), f. 22v (March 5, 1648, May 29, 1648), f. 23v (Aug. 20, 1648), f. 26v (April 26, 1649), f. 27r (June 17, 1649), f. 28v (Oct. 21, 1649), f. 30v (June 9, 1650), f. 35r (July 27, 1651), f. 36r (Dec. 14, 1651), ff. 37v-38r (June 7, 1652), f. 38r (June 18, 1652), f. 41r (Jan. 29, 1653 m.v.). On the House of Catechumens see E.N. ROTHMAN, *Becoming Venetian: conversion and transformation in the seventeenth-century Mediterranean*, in «Mediterranean Historical Review», 21, 1 (2006), pp.

39-75; P. IOLY ZORATTINI, *I nomi degli altri: conversioni a Venezia e nel Friuli Veneto in età moderna*, Firenze 2008.

⁴ According to historian Lovorka Čoralič, Andrea, son of Michael Nalosich, was an active member of the Dalmatian Confraternity in Venice from around 1655. An affluent businessman, he was involved in commerce between Venice and the island of Korčula, where he had some property. He is recorded for the last time in 1693 (personal communication).

⁵ For Maire's baptismal record, attesting to her religious instruction in her master's home (a rather uncommon practice), see ASPV, CRb, reg. 2, f. 26v (April 20, 1649). See also records attesting to her receipt of substantial sums from two funds dedicated to converts in Venice in 1657 and 1658 in ASPV, CRb, reg. 3, f. 16v (April 26, 1649, March 29, 1657, Sept. 9, 1658).

⁶ ASPV, Sezione Antica, *Examinum Matrimoniorum*, reg. 68, ff. 375r-379r (Aug. 20, 1670).

⁷ On spiritual kinship and patronage in general, see the pioneering and seminal work of S.W. MINTZ, E.R. WOLF, *An analysis of ritual co-parenthood (compadrazgo)*, in «Southwestern Journal of Anthropology», 6 (1950), pp. 341-68. On the patronage of converts, see ROTHMAN, *Becoming Venetian* cit.

⁸ On the role of spiritual kinship in regulating domestic service in Venice, see D. ROMANO, *Aspects of patronage in fifteenth- and sixteenth-century Venice*, in «Renaissance Quarterly», 46.4 (1993), pp. 712-33.

⁹ Nalosich may or may not have been responsible for the arrival in Venice in the late 1640s of two-dozen Muslim slaves from Zemonico – all of them women and young children. He was, however, mentioned as the master of at least three of them: Elena (b. 1624; baptized 1652), formerly Giulia, daughter of Bechir (quite possibly Omar and Maire's older sister), Antonia (b. 1634; baptized 1652), formerly Aise, daughter of Abib, and Margarita (b. 1636; baptized 1649), formerly Zeli, daughter of Xafer. ASPV, CRb, reg. 2, f. 26v (April 20, 1649), ff. 37v-38r (June 7, 1652).

¹⁰ The extent of slaves' social and spiritual integration, both before and after manumission, seems to have varied quite dramatically across the Italian peninsula. In some cities, ex-slaves could gain access to apprenticeships and marriage contracts with citizens, were welcome to take monastic vows or join tertiary orders, and in some cases even underwent beatification and canonization as saints. For such cases from early modern Palermo, see G. FIUME, *Il santo moro: i processi di canonizzazione di Benedetto da Palermo (1594-1807)*, Milan 2000 and EAD., *Schiavitù mediterranea* cit.; for Bologna, see R. SARTI, *Bolognesi schiavi dei «turchi» e schiavi «turchi» a Bologna tra Cinque e Settecento: alterità etnico-religiosa e riduzione in schiavitù*, in «Quaderni storici», 107 (2001), pp. 437-74; for Naples, see G. BOCCADAMO, *Tra croce e mezzaluna. Storie di schiavi*, in L. BARLETTA (a cura di), *Integrazione ed emarginazione. Circuiti e modelli. Italia e Spagna nei secoli XV-XVIII*, Napoli 2002, pp. 309-51.

¹¹ A. TENENTI, *Gli schiavi di Venezia alla fine de Cinquecento*, in «Rivista storica italiana», 67.1 (1955), pp. 52-69, esp. 52. On slavery in Venice proper and throughout the Venetian empire, see also C. VERLINDEN, *L'esclavage dans l'Europe médiévale*, vol. 2, Gent 1977; V. LAZARI, *Del traffico e delle condizioni degli schiavi in Venezia nei tempi di messo*, Turin 1862; D. ROMANO, *Housecraft and statecraft: domestic service in Renaissance Venice*, Baltimore 1996; S. MCKEE, *Inherited status and slavery in late medieval Italy and Venetian Crete*, in «Past and Present», 182 (2004), pp. 31-53.

¹² This inevitably tentative conclusion, based on research in the archives of the Pia Casa dei Catecumeni, accords well with the conclusions of Salvatore Bono, whose recent overview of the history and historiography of early modern slavery on the Italian peninsula argues for the centrality of the institution in a broader Mediterranean context. See S. BONO, *Schiavi in Italia: maghrebini, neri, slavi, ebrei e altri (secc. XVI-XIX)*, in «Mediterranea. Ricerche storiche», 19 (2010). Available URL: www.storiamediterranea.it/public/md1_dir/r1528.pdf; for a similar argument applied to an earlier period see also S. MCKEE, *Domestic slavery in Renaissance Italy*, in «Slavery & Abolition», 29.3 (2008), pp. 305-26.

¹³ P.H.D. KAPLAN, *Isabella d'Este and black African women*, in T.F. EARLE, K.J.P. LOWE (ed.), *Black Africans in Renaissance Europe*, Cambridge 2005, pp. 125-54, at 134. I have counted a total of 168 records of «Moors» baptized in the House of Catechumens throughout the period 1590-1670, almost all of them described as domestic slaves or their children. It seems reasonable to assume that Black slaves remained a fixture of elite Venetian households well into the eighteenth century.

¹⁴ See, for example, the case of Zuanne son of Zorzi Fantino, a fisherman from Faneromeni, who was captured by slave traders, sold to the Venetians, and served as a galley man for seventeen years before the Venetian Senate granted his petition to be released: Archivio di Stato di Venezia (henceforth: ASVe), *Senato Mar*, filza 98, unfoliated (Jan. 19, 1587 m.v.); or the case of the Armenian Saffar di Cachich, released from galley service after sixteen years thanks to the intervention of the Armenian merchant community in Venice: ASVe, *Collegio, Risposte di dentro*, b. 59, unfoliated (Dec. 5, 1612). This was far from a uniquely Venetian phenomenon. On the continued trafficking in Christian slaves throughout the Italian peninsula in the wake of Pius V's 1571 Papal bull *Licet omnibus*, which condemned those who captured Ottoman ships with Christian slaves and instead of liberating the cargo kept them in slavery, see SARTI, *Bolognesi schiavi* cit., p. 446.

¹⁵ For efforts to (temporarily) release slaves from prison or the galleys in anticipation of their baptism, see: Archivio delle Istituzioni di Ricovero e di Educazione, Venezia (henceforth: AIRE), *Catecumeni* (henceforth: CAT), B 4, f. 28r (Jan. 7, 1593 m.v.), f. 55v (Oct. 13, 1595), f. 100v (Dec. 2, 1599); B 6, f. 57v (Oct. 25, 1612), f. 63v (Jan. 18, 1612 m.v.).

¹⁶ On Venetian understandings of Ottoman slavery, see E.N. ROTHMAN, *Narrating conversion and subjecthood in the Venetian-Ottoman borderlands*, in L. STELLING, H. HENDRIX, T. RICHARDSON (ed.), *The turn of the soul: representations of religious conversion in early modern art and literature*, Leiden 2012, pp. 109-50.

¹⁷ On this aspect, and the web of institutions operating in Venice to redeem enslaved Venetians in Ottoman «Barbary», see R.C. DAVIS, *Slave redemption in Venice*, in J. MARTIN, D. ROMANO (ed.), *Venice reconsidered: the history and civilization of an Italian city-state, 1297-1797*, Baltimore 2000, pp. 454-87; A. PELIZZA, *Venezia e il riscatto degli schiavi in Età Moderna, secc. XVI-XVIII*, PhD dissertation, Università di Bologna, 2011. For the wider Mediterranean context of slave redemption, see also G. BONAFFINI, *Cattivi e redentori nel Mediterraneo tra 16. e 17. secolo*, Palermo 2003; G. BOCCADAMO, *Mercanti e schiavi fra Regno di Napoli, Barberia e Levante (secc. XVII-XVIII)*, in M. MAFRICI (a cura di), *Rapporti diplomatici e scambi commerciali nel Mediterraneo moderno*, Rubbettino 2005, pp. 237-74; W. KAISER (ed.), 2008; G.L. WEISS, *Captives and corsairs: France and slavery in the early modern Mediterranean*, Stanford 2011; D. HERSHENZON, *Early modern Spain and the creation of the Mediterranean: captivity, commerce, and knowledge*, PhD dissertation, University of Michigan, 2011.

¹⁸ See, among others, C.W. BRACEWELL, *The Uskoks of senj: piracy, banditry, and holy war in the sixteenth-century Adriatic*, Ithaca 1992; S. BONO, *Schiavi musulmani nell'Italia moderna. Galeotti, vu' cumprà, domestici*, Napoli 1999; L. LO BASSO, *Schiavi, forzati e buonevoglie. La gestione dei rematori delle galere dell'Ordine di Santo Stefano e della Repubblica di Venezia. Modelli a confronto*, in *L'Ordine di Santo Stefano e il mare*, Pisa 2001, pp. 169-232; G. POUmarede, *Pour en finir avec la Croisade. Mythes et réalités de la lutte contre les Turcs aux XVI^e et XVII^e siècles*, Paris 2004; M. GREENE, *Catholic pirates and Greek merchants: a maritime history of the Mediterranean*, Princeton 2010.

¹⁹ As a highly autonomous chapter of the Roman Inquisition, the Venetian Holy Office (reorganized in 1547) was administered by and large by local patrician clerics, who, as scions of the ruling elite, often conflated reason of state with doctrinal orthodoxy, or at least put a premium on ensuring the former. This venetocentric patrician perspective shaped both the choice of cases that the Holy Office ultimately pursued, and the nature of the documentation produced as a result, and should therefore be borne in mind as we follow the unfolding of Zorzi's interrogation. For a bibliography on this well-studied institution, see G. RUGGIERO, *The strange death of Margarita Marcellini: male, signs, and the everyday world of pre-modern medicine*, in «American Historical Review», 106.4 (2001), pp. 1141-58, n. 3.

²⁰ Marcantonio was one of the six sons of Domenico Falier (1492-1564) and Chiara Contarini, a patrician couple of rather modest means. The couple married in 1541, suggesting that in 1573 Marcantonio was a fairly young man. The fact that in visiting the slave's place of hiding he brought along his brother Luca (b. 1545), himself a young man who had not yet embarked upon a career, suggests either Marcantonio's even humbler position (and possibly younger age), or his sense that a group visit might command more respect. On the Faliere, see R. TARGHETTA, *Falier, Domenico*, in «Dizionario Biografico degli Italiani», vol. 44, Rome 1994, pp. 423-4 and IDEM, *Falier, Luca*, in «Dizionario Biografico degli Italiani», vol. 44, Rome 1994, pp. 426-7.

²¹ From the opening statement in ASVe, Santo Uffizio, *Processi* (henceforth: SUP, b. 35, fasc. 12 (Aug. 15, 1573), f. 1r.

²² On trans-imperial subjects, see ROTHMAN, *Brokering empire* cit.

²³ Like Zorzi's master, the inquisitors sitting on the case were themselves, for the most part, Venetian patricians.

²⁴ ASVe, SUP 35, Zorzi's testimony, Aug. 15, 1573, ff. 1v-4r.

²⁵ In theory, if not in practice, Venetians were not supposed to trade in – and certainly not to possess – Christian slaves. If this moral dictum was overlooked as a matter of course when it came to recent converts to Christianity, it was harder to ignore when a slave could prove he or she had been born to Christian parents. Not surprisingly, claiming to have been kidnapped from Christian parents at tender age was a very common trope in inquisitorial depositions by slaves in Venetian households, and elsewhere on the Italian peninsula, who sought manumission or who attempted to justify their escape. See, for example, the case of the runaway Fattema in Naples in 1667, discussed in G. BOCCADAMO, *Napoli e l'Islam. Storie di musulmani, schiavi e rinnegati in età moderna*, Napoli 2010, pp. 209-10. See also GREENE, *Catholic pirates* cit., p. 161.

²⁶ Head shaving and the wearing of «Turkish» clothes was widely regarded by early modern Venetians as signs of conversion to Islam. Significantly, change in dress was similarly held to be a sign of a convert's new religious affiliation in the Ottoman Empire. See A. MINKOV, *Conversion to Islam in the Balkans: Kısve Babası petitions and ottoman social life, 1670-1730*, Leiden 2004, and, for a more sustained discussion of the process of joining Islamic communities in the early modern Ottoman Balkans, T. KRSTIĆ, *Contested conversions to Islam: narratives of religious change in the early modern Ottoman Empire*, Stanford 2011. For the relationship between outward appearance and presumed inner spiritual transformation in early modern Venice, see also R.C. HEAD, *Religious boundaries and the Inquisition in Venice: trials of jews and judaizers, 1548-1580*, in «Journal of Medieval and Renaissance Studies», 20.2 (1990), pp. 175-204; B. WILSON, *Reflecting on the face of the Turk in sixteenth-century venetian portrait books*, in «Word & Image», 19.1 & 2 (2003), pp. 38-58.

²⁷ SUP 35, Frangia's testimony, Aug. 20, 1573, ff. 6r-6v.

²⁸ SUP 35, Frangia's testimony, Aug. 20, 1573, ff. 6r-6v.

²⁹ Concern over food restrictions and their violations typified the Holy Office's attempts to expose and uproot heresy, and Giulia was clearly conscious of the link between the violation of Catholic food restrictions and heresy. On the Venetian Holy Office's interest in food consumption as index of religious (un)orthodoxy in the age of confessionalization, see HEAD, *Religious Boundaries* cit.

³⁰ ASVe, *Cinque Savii, Seconda serie*, b. 187, fasc. 1, unfoliated (1574). While Frangia, his son, and eventually his grandson all served as custodians of this institution, it only became mandatory for Ottoman Muslim merchants to lodge there in 1621.

³¹ ROTHMAN, *Brokering empire* cit., pp. 198-210.

³² For a sustained discussion of this point, and the broader issue of trans-imperial mediation, see E.N. ROTHMAN, *Genealogies of mediation: «culture broker» and imperial governmentality*, in E. MURPHY, D.W. COHEN ET AL. (ed.), *Anthrobistory: unsettling knowledge, questioning discipline*, Ann Arbor 2010, pp. 67-79.

³³ ASPV, CRb, reg. 1, f. 5v (June 23, 1591).

³⁴ ROTHMAN, *Becoming Venetian* cit., pp. 42, 58.

³⁵ ASVe, SUP, b. 55, unfoliated (Aug. 8, 1585).

³⁶ On Ottoman domestic slavery, see E. TOLEDANO, *Slavery and abolition in the Ottoman Middle East*, Seattle 1998; E.G. FRIEDMAN, *Christian captives at «hard labor» in Algiers, 16th-18th Centuries*, in «The International Journal of African Historical Studies», 13.4 (1980), pp. 616-32.

³⁷ ASVe, *Senato, Deliberazioni Costantinopoli*, reg. 23, fasc. 2, ff. 64r-66v (Oct. 8, 1636).

³⁸ On the Knights of Malta, see GREENE, *Catholic pirates* cit., esp. pp. 95-98.

³⁹ ASVe, SUP, b. 105, unfoliated (March 30, 1649).

⁴⁰ ROTHMAN, *Brokering empire* cit., pp. 229-30, 239.

⁴¹ Cf. S. EPSTEIN, *Speaking of Slavery: Color, Ethnicity, and Human Bondage in Italy*, Ithaca 2001.